

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF SYNERGETIC APPROACH IN PRIMARY EDUCATION CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article provides scientific and practical information about improving the knowledge of primary school teachers, developing their mental thinking and thinking based on a synergistic approach in education classes.

Keywords: *pedagogical, synergetic approach, primary education, self-determination, self-education, modern knowledge, methods.*

As a result of global changes in the world education system, the attention to education of a free citizen personality is aimed at guiding young people towards social relations, developing such qualities as humanism, tolerance, social intelligence, communicativeness in interaction with people. In order for learners to gain social experience, to realize their natural abilities, to follow the principles of patriotism, respect for national traditions, openness, civility, generosity, politeness in interpersonal relations, to develop methodologies aimed at developing these qualities. great importance is attached. In the leading educational institutions of developed countries, large-scale work is being carried out to educate young people who think independently, have modern knowledge and skills, and have a strong life position. As the Republic of Uzbekistan stabilizes its independence on a global scale year by year, its prospects depend on the development of educated, spiritually mature people of today's generation. At this point, the science of psychology and pedagogy and its correctness

in practice are very important to further increase the effectiveness of forming a full-fledged, active, well-rounded person for the human psyche. We can say that the social sphere is especially based on education, while our society is rapidly developing and its economic and political status is increasing day by day. Reforms are being carried out in the education system as well as in all areas. At the heart of these reforms, upbringing and education of the young generation is defined as one of the most important tasks. A vivid example of this is President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev's statement, "Another important issue that keeps us thinking is related to the manners, behavior, and, in a word, worldview of our youth. Today, the times are rapidly changing... The youth are the ones who feel these changes the most. May the youth be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, he should not forget his identity. Let the call that we are the descendants of great nobles resonate in their hearts and encourage them to stay true to themselves. How can we achieve this? "Education, education only at the expense of education" is of great importance. Because education of students is very important for improving the quality of education and the educational process. Because of this, we can say that the introduction of the science of "Education" in school institutions was appropriate. Education, like the environment, is one of the external factors affecting human development. The feature of education is that it is carried out regularly under the guidance of an educator, aiming at a specific goal and forming positive qualities in a person.

In today's modern education, the organization of lessons based on new approaches has a significant impact on the effectiveness of lessons, the post-noclassical stage of the development of science is reflected in determining its perspective, new directions and terms are entering the sciences. Including the term "synergetics" is organized by scientists as a new direction. . In the 70s of the 20th century, synergetics began to be formed as an interdisciplinary scientific direction. The scope of scientific and methodological issues of synergetics is aimed at finding such strategic development mechanisms of science. However, the aspects of this approach to the problem that are still controversial are recognized by various scientific experts. Such debates help to

shed light on the undiscovered aspects of synergetics. The synergetic approach is based on the superiority of self-education, self-organization and self-management in educational activities, self-discovery and improvement, self- consists in stimulating or stimulating influence on the subject for the purpose of understanding. This, "pedagogical synergetics" is a new direction of pedagogical knowledge, which is based on the laws of self-organization and development of educational systems. Pedagogical synergetics allows a new approach to the development of self- determination and personality development problems in terms of openness, co-creation and orientation to self-development. GM Kojaspirova, the concept of "synergetics" is very close to the concept of "education" (translated from Greek, it means "joint action", "cooperation"). A synergistic understanding of the world is important in educating a person: a synergistic way of thinking is characterized by openness, dialogism and communication. Synergetics directs parents to study the most complex internal laws of human life as subjects of the virtual-pedagogical process. Synergetic education, like the new pedagogy, means self-education, self-determination that stimulates a person's potential.

The synergetic approach allows to consider each subject of the pedagogical process (parent, student, teacher) as self-developing subsystems that make the transition from development to self-development. Therefore, the formation of the pedagogical culture of parents is one of the most important tasks of modern society, it should be a part of the state social policy. is closely related to the training of highly qualified personnel who will contribute to the rapid development. Accordingly, it is important and necessary to educate every student in the oriental spirit, based on the students of social development. For elementary school students, this period is a period of intellectual development based on figurative thinking. There is no doubt that this is mainly done in the educational process. We cannot conclude that other aspects of the personality do not develop during this educational process. We strive to establish a developmental pathway that is leading to elementary school students. Because the youth are the future of our country. Due to the independence of Uzbekistan, the wise

stories of our forefathers about morals and manners are gaining importance in forming the moral values of young people.

In conclusion, it should be said that the study of scientific-theoretical views on the basis of a synergistic approach among educational subjects is important for everyone. Because, first of all, independence gave us the right to live freely. After all, the right to live freely should not remain just a concept in people's minds. We need to fully understand it, feel it and be able to apply it correctly in practice. Only then will we make our contribution to the eternal independence of our country.

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